

Title: What qualitative data would do to machine learning pipelines.

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Abstract:

Qualitative data is collected in the behavioral science but not yet used in machine learning pipelines. In this paper, we will discuss under which technical and epistemic circumstances an integration would be feasible. The running examples are taken from a study in a nursing home on how shared spaces are used by residents.

We first present how qualitative data can be incorporated into machine learning pipelines, for example to reduce the search space or as additional predictor variables. This process would require tokenization and turning qualitative data into numbers. We will highlight limitations and epistemic risks associated with this process.

In the second part of the paper we will focus on the epistemic feasibility. Given the difference in methods underlying the creation of quantitative and qualitative data, we will attempt to describe epistemic clashes and propose a mitigation strategy.

We will discuss if a tokenization would be able to carry context and interpretation ingrained in qualitative data over into the output of the machine learning pipeline. Would this be a favorable outcome from a machine learning perspective? What would this mean for the creators of the qualitative data and their interpretations? Can we dissect the creation of qualitative data from its interpretation and what would that mean for a mixed machine learning pipeline?

As a mitigation strategy, we suggest to learn from the rigor of qualitative research methods when it comes to describing biases, beliefs and assumptions of the people performing research. We will sketch a way to translate some of those tools and protocols to describe the development of machine learning pipelines, including decision making around which data is considered as input. A clear description where and what data is used, and what the expected, inherited context is (i.e. what bias we are introducing), might open up the use of qualitative data in machine learning pipelines while respecting epistemic differences.